

The Knowledge Commons in the age of AI: opportunities and risks for urban smart learning

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Abstract. This paper reflects on the state of the knowledge commons in the age of artificial intelligence (AI), broadly revisiting areas discussed in prior work by the author concerning human and non-human interactions with place-based knowledge in contexts of informal urban smart learning [1, 2]. The knowledge commons is loosely regarded as all the open, free-access knowledge content available to anyone via the Internet, both amateur and expert knowledge. Smarter urban citizen learning is framed here in terms of accessing knowledge information efficiently at point of need in an urbanised built environment, where knowledge might be readily provided through suitable technical infrastructures. Knowledge mapping, seeking and interactions, push/pull knowledge delivery, recommender system criteria, significance of serendipity, personalised knowledge management and other related issues are considered in the context of artificial intelligence technology capabilities and potential risks. Technical infrastructure is conceptualised as a reasonable interpretive imaginary of what smart ad-hoc urban learning could become, in a civically owned, interoperable, app agnostic platform designed for any kind of citizen learning and collaboration (for example described in [3, 4]). The position of the paper seeks a balanced criticality for perspectives on both AI data analysis and generative AI content, additionally acknowledging that AI technologies as they relate to the knowledge commons for urban smart learning could potentially act in a context of custodianship for governance of the digital knowledge commons as a public good.

Keywords: smart learning, urban learning, knowledge commons, artificial intelligence, generative AI, semantic web

1 Introduction

This paper has come about due to aspects arising from prior research by the author concerning human and non-human interactions with place-based knowledge in ‘smart learning journeys’, and participant reported experiences of learning as they described [1]. Technical issues highlighted in an earlier article by the author [2] lay the ground for the scope of this paper, which considers how AI technologies may support urban citizen interactions with the digital knowledge commons (KC) as part of ad-hoc learning in urban environments. A balanced criticality is adopted to estimate both opportunities and risks of AI technologies. In general, all mention of the KC is assumed in

this paper to refer to the digital knowledge commons, though this is made more explicit where relevant.

Artificial intelligence (AI) data analysis may bring advantages to place-based knowledge discoverability and delivery in several key areas. For example, anonymised recommender systems and information management of digital knowledge at micro to macro scale [5], and the affordances of AI analysis to more accurately recognise and identify geographical location information via images or textual content for geotagging¹ and findability of place-based knowledge [6–8]. Language translation using embedded technologies can provide seamless multilingual geo-content interactions and collaborations [8], and AI powered personalised learning for search and retrieval of knowledge content (e.g. [9]). Yet these advantages may be outweighed by challenges arising from AI technologies, such as disincentivising user contributions in collective knowledge bases [10], influx of low quality or ‘deepfake’ generative AI (GenAI) content in the KC (e.g. [11]), and ‘superficial evaluations’ due to algorithmically simplistic, ‘reductivist’ decision making in the open knowledge sphere [12, 13].

In smart city urban contexts the technically infused built environment can offer multiple opportunities for embedding potential digitally supported interactions with knowledge, information communication, and citizen collaboration and contributions. The ubiquity of smartphone ownership, geospatial technologies, extended reality and IoT functionalities can provide users with access to knowledge collections for various interactions (e.g. [14]). However, smart learning cities in terms of immersive learning technologies remain a more theoretical concept than a manifested reality [15]. What follows here therefore is a reasonable interpretive imaginary of what smart ad-hoc urban learning *could become*, in the context of seamless interaction with the KC, enhanced by advanced technologies including AI tools and analysis systems embedded in the built environment. Within this scope, smart learning city technical infrastructure might be a civically owned, interoperable, app-agnostic platform designed for any kind of citizen learning and collaboration [3, 4].

Paper structure

Inspired and motivated by the context of prior work and publications by the author, the paper adopts a conceptual analysis debate utilising literature relevant to urban smart learning contexts. Following sections provide a short definition of the KC and of urban smarter learning pertinent to debate in the paper, before moving on to reflect on the practical aspects of urban ad-hoc learning and the possibilities of ‘what could come next’ in AI learning cities and urban citizen connectivity with the KC. Subsequent debate considers aspects of the maintenance and custodianship of the KC and further context of KC value, acknowledging relevant considerations such as data value, environmental cost, demand for energy, and financial cost of developing AI technologies. Concluding remarks reflect on the changing definition of the KC, and its

¹ Geotagging applications such as Geotagging.ai, Geospy.ai and others are discussed later in the paper

role in society as a foundation of democratic participatory citizenry and a global digital public good.

2 Defining the knowledge commons

The ‘knowledge commons’ (KC) generally refers to all public domain, open access, commons licensed and free-to-access open knowledge and information on the Internet, including user generated ‘collective knowledge’ in forums, wikis and domain specific platforms, as well as open-access expert knowledge. The digital KC is regarded as a ‘commons resource’ because everyone can use and contribute to the resource without restriction, while not diminishing it for others, in this way the ‘language of the commons’ can be applied [16]. Hess describes the commons as “a new way of looking at what is shared or should be shared in the world around us”, noting the KC as ‘a vast and complex sector’, and that “(i)n many cases knowledge became a commons when it became digital. It has unique characteristics as a commons. For the most part, it is a renewable resource” [16]. Digital KC resources are widely considered as all the ‘*digital stuff*’ [17], created by people who may have attached an explicit intellectual property open license to it², or the vast amounts of free-to-access content that have no explicit copyright terms attached. It is a moot point that though this non-licensed material would legally be considered fully copyrighted, it is freely available to any user of the Internet to benefit from. As Lane points out, “(i)n principle, all stuff can be given an educational purpose” [17], which in the case of this paper is interpreted as urban context just-in-time ad-hoc interaction with knowledge available via the Internet at point of need.

Blogs, topic interest websites or YouTube videos are all popular content online, and free or open-licensed Internet knowledge arguably forms the backbone of the Internet in the increasingly content hungry media culture of recent years [18]. However, somewhat paralleling Lane’s statement in 2008 [17], this paper is not directly concerned with individual author rights issues in relation to Internet content. What is of interest (along with many other things) is how the KC may be impacted by mass reuse for Large Language Model (LLM) training data and how this might impact the KC longer term (e.g. [10]).

2.1 Digital knowledge as a commons

To understand the nature of a ‘commons’, Bruun [19] discusses ownership of the urban (land) commons and begins her argument with an illustration of the pressure of competing interests between individual need, potential for gainful profit and maintaining a community resource - in this case cooperative housing for the benefit of all. Bruun cites Gudeman [20]:

² Usually a CC license <https://creativecommons.org/share-your-work/cclicenses/>

“A commons is regulated through moral obligations that have the backing of a powerful sanction. But communities are hardly homes of equality and altruism, and they provide ample space for the assertion of power and exploitation from patriarchy to feudal servitude” ([20]).

Gudeman’s words perfectly demonstrate the challenge of maintaining the digital KC as a resource for all in the face of the “monolithic model landscape dominated by just a few developers”, producing potential for vast financial profit by ‘a handful of private companies’, imbalancing the power consensus for safeguarding custodianship for use and access by all [10]. However, it would be disingenuous to assume that this power might only be to do harm. As Berlingeur points out, “however counter-intuitive it may seem, there can be forms of capitalistic competition that are based on the creation of commons” [21]. Berlingeur examines the trajectory of Free and Open Source Software (FOSS) cultures in terms of the fluctuating nature of free labour, ownership, expertise and economic value. When considering that the biggest players in the FOSS community may now be the biggest technology companies such as Microsoft, Google, IBM or Facebook [21], it is worth considering how wealthy privately owned AI companies may over time seek a similar role within the digital commons of knowledge, to contribute to and use the knowledge in the pool in equal measure. Hess draws attention to prior work analysing the intellectual public domain as a commons, and “increasing legal ambiguities in the advent of the online digital environment” [16]. She cites several authors from 1995-97 that ‘apply the language of the commons to various aspects of the Internet, and perhaps importantly, acknowledges Lohmann’s work (e.g. [22]) equating the non-profit sector with the commons as influential for understanding the ‘collaborative nature of philanthropy’ [16]. This perhaps provides impetus for considering the importance of the economic potential value of the digital KC resource. Within discussions about the digital KC and the role(s) of AI and GenAI, a significant factor is that of financial gain and economic power. But to devalue the commons resource that may provide the most value to the companies is counter intuitive and may in fact provide the impetus for technology companies to act as guardians of quality, authenticity and openness of that resource.

2.2 The knowledge commons as an epistemic right

Epistemic rights are the rights of citizens to access knowledge and information equally so as to make decisions and form opinions from a position of understanding and awareness, and digital epistemic rights in a democratic society form part of building more solid and maintainable individual democratic engagement and responsibility [23]. It might be reasonable to include the KC as part of these considerations, perhaps more particularly in the age of AI technological impact. If it is correct to consider the KC as a *commons*, we might then assume we have rights to it, in the way of “common pool resources and common property regimes” [16], with a right to use and contribute in a cooperative ownership [24]. It may be fair to consider the whole of the KC as a collective intelligence collaborative resource, and a ‘public good’, in the sense of crowdsourced KC [10, 25]. In this way the right to a KC, fostered and maintained

under a trusted custodianship, may be seen as a digital epistemic right, and perhaps AI technologies and companies may play a role in the future custodianship of the KC, in a human-centred ‘friendly AI’ model [26, 27].

3 Defining urban smart learning

To understand the present terrain of urban smart learning, it is good to briefly revisit the past. Dede described millennial learning as multi-media, virtual and augmented realities, and communal, collaborative learning with “diverse, tacit, situated experience” [28]. Together with Dunleavy, Dede further expanded on location aware and visually triggered augmented reality in learning contexts [29]. These works outline early concepts of urban smart learning, and subsequent literature within the smart cities domain complemented these ideas [30–33]. Much (though not all) of this work concerned what might be described as didactic formal learning, where students participate in instructionally designed tasks with set learning outcomes. As debate around smart cities and learning cities evolved, citizen-centred urban learning was acknowledged to sometimes have broader contexts as social, ad-hoc knowledge seeking interactions, with no set tasks, tutors or pedagogical design [34]. For example within the most basic context of learning, where “all stuff can be given an educational purpose” [17], even any simple use of a Google search engine can be interpreted as the beginning of a learning experience [35]. Though not intended as a comprehensive summarisation, knowledge seeking while in urban places that may be of relevance to this paper might be described loosely in three ways:

- Quick and factual - e.g. direct questions about immediate point of need or interest, e.g. information about places and buildings, transport information, emergency help, local entertainments etc.;
- Resource compiling - e.g. finding specific types of amenities and services in a local area such as health and social care information, job centres, kindergartens, college courses, special needs facilities etc.;
- As part of activities or local interest pursuits – e.g. heritage and tourism trails, local community group initiatives, guides and information etc.

Urban smart learning therefore, is framed here in terms of accessing knowledge information in an urbanised built environment, where place-related knowledge might be readily provided through suitable technical infrastructure. Learning manifests through the engagement, intrinsic motivation and sense of value or usefulness for the participant learner citizen, depending on the level of complexity of information seeking. [36].

4 Human and non-human knowledge interactions

Place-related (geospatial) urbanised learning and user interactions with the digital KC can be loosely grouped according to human and machine function and interaction.

Human entity machine assisted factors may be human language multi-translation, user-defined personalisation and information organisation, social communication, and human-to-human connections. Machine readable entity factors may include smarter metadata or other machine readable properties enabling geo-spatially referenced (geo-tagged) knowledge content, record of authenticity (provenance factors), versioning, mark of quality, and properties such as topic label, subject area or level of expertise. Further desirable criteria for functionality would be technical interoperability between platforms, knowledge content, devices and things, and enhanced intelligent human and non-human findability and recommendations. Advanced interactions that may need to increasingly happen might be fact checking, source finding and deepfake or GenAI detection mechanisms. Following sections reflect on some key areas of how users may interact with digital knowledge in place, and the non-human mechanisms that support and assist these processes.

4.1 Organising the Knowledge Commons

Intelligent search, smart knowledge taxonomies, optimised efficient recommender systems and personalised retrieval preferences are all ways that ad-hoc urban learning can be made smarter through better management of knowledge and interaction with it. For example, the ‘emerging artificial intelligence capabilities’ of knowledge management for finding and retrieving knowledge, organising information repositories at scale, synthesis of existing knowledge or generating new knowledge through deep learning techniques, derived and generated from billions of pieces of training information [5, 37–39].

Knowledge graphs organise informational entities at scale, and are utilised in the development of AI applications and functionality. Of interest to this paper is the place-related knowledge that can be useful to the urban ad-hoc learner, providing them with efficient, reliable accurate information. Geospatial location of image or text-based knowledge content is pertinent to requirements for sourcing knowledge to develop understanding about geo-localised features, events, social trends, crisis or emergencies, educational and learning purposes. Geospatial knowledge graphs are relational representations of ‘spatial entities’ and attributes, and “help facilitate many geospatial applications such as geographic question answering, geospatial interoperability, and geospatial knowledge discovery” (GeoKG 2022³). Zhu [40] describes a geospatial KG as a “graph-based data format (that) lays the foundation for creating a "FAIR" (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) environment, facilitating the management and analysis of geographic information”. In geospatial knowledge graphs, nodes can be connected to other datasets to create multimodal relationships that are then absorbed into larger KGs, associating spatial knowledge with other factors. This would appear a natural part of organising geospatial knowledge into dynamic searchable content able to be utilised in place-related knowledge recommender

³ 1st ACM SIGSPATIAL International Workshop on Geospatial Knowledge Graphs <https://geokg-sigspatial.github.io/geokg2022/>

systems. Though Sheth et al. [41] note that many KGs are “proprietary and expensive for usage by academia or industry researchers and small clients”, they also remark that ‘Federal, industry, and academia’ have proposed an Open Knowledge Network “to provide a nation-scale open infrastructure linking cross-domain information of relevant entities”. Perhaps then, open KGs might include geospatial open KGs (e.g. The Urban Flooding Open Knowledge Network⁴) as part of KG resources, and work with the capabilities of ‘GeoAI’ techniques to facilitate extraction of geographic information from unstructured (textual) data, such as news articles and Wikipedia [42], thus enabling provision of geospatial related knowledge at unprecedented scale and accuracy.

4.2 Discoverability of place-based knowledge

Visualised geo-matched information perhaps has “the potential to redefine how people use AI” [43] as a way to navigate and surface relevant search results related to place. Brief examination of literature and commercial developments in this area suggest the power of AI to either apply geotagging⁵ information to content automatically at source, or ‘describe what it sees’ in images and recognise in textual descriptions the places that are being referred to, potentially annotating location information using AI advanced machine learning techniques.

Nizzoli et al.’s [7] work focuses on ‘Online Social Networks’ (OSN), that “convey rich information about geospatial facets of reality”, but “lacks explicit and structured geographic information”. They use ‘Geo-Semantic Parsing’ to extract geographic information via a combination of AI techniques and ‘rich, structured, interconnected data in multiple knowledge graphs’ to geotag pre-annotated OSN content. Various commercial applications now leverage the power of visual search and image geotagging for understanding geospatial characteristics, and naming their location or attaching geotags. Open AI’s GPT4-V⁶, Geotagging AI⁷, GeoSpy⁸ or NetOwl⁹ work with large datasets, analysing images or textual data using mixtures of deep learning, annotated data, contextual geo-information and heuristics factors to achieve related place recognition and association of textual and image content. Paul et al.’s work discusses use of free and open source software (FOSS) based methods to achieve client-side image geotagging from within smartphones as a means of image geotags being generated at source and then utilised with WebGIS services for further use [6]. This may allow smaller scale and less costly ways to utilise AI visual search, important in light

⁴ Urban Flooding Open Knowledge Network <https://ufokn.com/https://ufokn.com/>

⁵ Geotagging: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Geotagging>

⁶ OpenAI GPT-V <https://www.pcmag.com/explainers/what-is-chatgpt-vision-gpt-4v>

⁷ GeoTagging AI <https://geotagging.ai/>

⁸ GeoSpy <https://api.geospy.ai/>

⁹ NetOwl <https://www.netowl.com/>

of (for example) GPT4-V being only available in premium tier functionality for \$20 per month at time of writing.

As Nizzoli et al. [7] remark, wider availability of geotagged content “would open up the possibility to develop new and better geospatial services and applications”, and these techniques hint at the possibilities of geospatial knowledge being integrated with other related information, so that spatially related information might be searched and interpreted within rich and diverse urban environments and contexts.

4.3 Recommendations and geospatial knowledge

The scope of AI visual and place-name or description text search and analysis might be envisaged to be incorporated into more advanced recommender systems, where smartphone location sensing affordances offer integration with built environment embedded technologies. This might be applied to push/pull scenarios for smart delivery of geotagged knowledge directly to a device, either triggered via geospatial phone applications and Internet of Things sensors, or via human search retrieval. In user requested pull information retrieval, it is the quality, depth, diversity and potential for serendipity of search results that are significant. In push scenarios, where information is not directly solicited by a user, it is the pre-selection and automation mechanism that is of significance.

Recommender system methods such as those outlined for example in Hu [39] can already provide a personalised, optimised search using ‘hybrid recommendation algorithms’ that combine content-based filtering, collaborative filtering, user behaviour characteristics, and various deep learning algorithms. ‘Convolutional Neural Networks’, ‘Recurrent Neural Networks’ or ‘Transformer’ process image and text or analyse sequential data to accurately rank and recommend search results. Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) “can learn to generate content that meets the needs and interests of users, thereby improving the performance of search engines and user experience” [39]. Ge et al. [44] regard recommender systems as “at the forefront of Human-centered AI”, and that “despite their enormous capabilities and potential... may also lead to undesired effects”. They argue there are growing concerns for compromised user trust due to non-transparency, unfair treatment of different users, producers, or platforms, privacy concerns due to extensive use of user’s private data, and lack of user controllability, all contributing to an expanding list of ‘untrustworthy issues’ [44]. Undertaking a comprehensive literature review of over 400 representative papers on the ‘core aspects of trustworthiness’, a consensus emerges for ‘pivotal dimensions’ of trustworthiness as explainability, fairness, privacy, robustness, and controllability [44]. These dimensions complement issues raised by Duricic et al. [45], who highlight diversity, serendipity and fairness as more significant overall than accuracy of recommendation results. Fairness and diversity of opinions and sources foster more serendipity, and fairness of source means smaller platforms or datasets may be included as equal source value. Ziarani & Ravanmehr [46] also note that too much recommendation accuracy can result in over-specialisation and become ‘bor-

ing’, that novelty and diversity offer partly useful solutions but may not produce relevant results. Unexpectedness and relevance make for criteria that lead to appealing and useful recommendations, therefore usefulness of serendipitous recommendations are the main criteria for successful recommendations.

Various work in AI enhanced techniques for recommendations, anonymised user data, improved autonomy, personalisation or as recommendation frameworks to act ‘as controllers’ indicate many relevant factors of advanced recommendation system developments. Limited space here can only touch on possibilities debated in the literature in this complex terrain to provide broad insight of issues at hand (e.g. [47–49]).

4.4 Human and non-human personalisation and collaboration

Jarrahi et al. [5] reflect on personalised knowledge management using AI enhanced mechanisms for the creation, storage, retrieval, sharing and application of knowledge. Envisaging humans and AI in partnership, mixtures of AI agents and learned human behaviours foster ‘a symbiotic relationship between humans and AI’ to manage knowledge dynamically, in personalised ways. Personal enquiry is supported by personal intelligent assistants that are self-learning, interactive systems that can learn and refine their interactions with the user over time, providing dynamic knowledge needs, workflows, preferences, and feedback for individualised solutions [5]. Whilst the context of Jarrahi et al.’s work is organisational knowledge management, the principles of their proposed system are well suited to urban smart learning technological provision at scale, though anonymisation of users may still be a challenge. However, solutions such as those described in Rao et al. [50] propose a “novel privacy-preserving framework for location recommendation based on federated learning, a decentralized collaborative machine learning technique”, and that all user related ‘check-in’ data remains on the users device rather than a centralised database. A “location recommendation model is then deployed on each user's device to locally train the data and model location preferences”, with further spatio-temporal and auxiliary public data to improve location recommendation accuracy [50]. Of note, Vannieuwenhuyze et al. [51] warn of the danger of too much personalisation in urban recommender systems, particularly in geospatially localised contexts, where limited homogeneous suggestions result in ‘urban filter bubbles’, echo chambers of bias or favouritism (popularity bias).

Pérez-Ortiz et al. [9] describe ‘X5Learn’, an intriguing ‘personalised learning companion’ that operates as a ‘suite of interconnected tools’ to navigate open educational resources with enhanced recommendation, transcription, annotation and user interface interaction functionalities. Though aimed more readily at formal learning contexts, X5Learn incorporates key factors that might be adopted at scale for more informal ad-hoc knowledge interaction use-cases. For example, AI processed video section fragmentation with auto-generated annotation connected to related Wikipedia concepts [52]. This avoids manual labelling for human-readable annotations, and is

“future-proof as Wikipedia ... evolves with the ever changing universal knowledge” [9].

The meaning of ‘universal knowledge’ in the context of Pérez-Ortiz et al. is reasonable to assume refers to the digital KC, and might also be described as online collective intelligence (CI). Burton et al. [10] consider crowdsourced knowledge platforms and image-based commons¹⁰ as CI, and note that LLM output can deter individuals from engaging with original source material or making new contributions in these collective commons platforms by removing the transparency of how individual contributions are handled. When transparency of individual contribution is lost it acts as a strong disincentive to contribute, as it is no longer clear whether and how contributions are recognized. Therefore the widespread use of LLMs as “substitutes for these collective KC could create an information environment that undermines this form of CI” ([53] in [10]). Other notable LLM impact issues raised by Burton et al. include the positives of increase in accessibility and inclusion in collaboration, accelerating idea generation and aggregating information across a group. Key harms are listed as propagating illusions of consensus, reducing functional diversity among individuals and removing friction in the production of false or misleading information [10].

4.5 Smart translation and communication

At time of writing there is increasing availability of sophisticated, almost instantaneous translation between numerous languages in digital context integrations, made possible using AI enhanced technologies and big data sources. Consider technologies such as the widely available DeepL¹¹, for example used in Mastodon social media servers¹², or PixelChat¹³, a new startup collaboration between academia and private enterprise, for ‘real time’ translation between users. However, the significance of some languages being more prevalent in LLM datasets than others remains a challenge, which impacts the effectiveness of chatbot interaction, search results and machine translation (MT) capabilities. The codes of human language in use of tone, emotion, unspoken context and colloquial expressions to construct latent meaning in human conversation are already a significant challenge in human-to-human contexts. Rubin and Rubin [54] summarise this well, and shed light on the challenges facing MT in less utilised low-resource language datasets. “Language translation is not a simple linguistic exercise. Cultural and contextual interpretation always plays its part, because the meanings of words often carry subtle nuances and cultural connotations that have to be captured in translation. A complex situation can arise where it is impossible to express the concept in different languages with precise equivalency” [54].

¹⁰ For example, Wikipedia and Stack Overflow, Flickr and Shutterstock

¹¹ DeepL Integrations <https://www.deepl.com/en/products/integrations>

¹² DeepL API config for Mastodon servers <https://write.as/sweetmeat/how-to-activate-the-mastodon-v4-deepl-api-text-translation-service>

¹³ PixelChat partners <https://www.pixelchat.online/why-choose-us>

Thompson et al. [55] note that “content on the web is often translated into many languages”, and “the low quality of these multi-way translations indicates they were likely created using Machine Translation”. This indicates that languages not dominant in the LLM model training data may return much less accurate output due to low quality data for training, though some work shows that smaller ‘low-resource language sets can achieve good results (e.g. [56–58]).

Esposito [59] poses the provocative question of whether or not communicating directly with algorithms - chatbots - means that they can potentially be considered as conversational partners. She posits that when we communicate with digital personal assistants, the information we get did not exist before, until we requested it, and as such, imitates the behaviour of an interactive conversational partner. But in this case, “the partner is not a human being, but a machine”. She argues that pervasive use of chatbot communication services means that increasingly we communicate directly with chatbots in daily life and have already normalised this activity, and if a user is getting the information they need, they do not care whether one partner is non-human. In terms of voice search query or collaboration with non-human partners in generating new knowledge, this offers flexible new ways of developing ideas and understanding, in a collaboration with chatbots that have a ‘semblance of contingency’ and ‘unpredictability’ of responses [59]. These ideas are somewhat supported in Casebourne et al., who discuss CI in terms of collective decision making and problem solving, and refer to AI chatbots in the context of dialogue partners who act as coaches, ‘personas’ or evaluate communication activities in for example collaborative teamwork [60].

Of concern, it may be argued that increased use of AI chatbot communication and data surveillance gathering foster a culture of digital interactions user voyeurism and loss of human context. This loss can impact search interpretation, serendipity, loss of human empathy and understanding, and deep loss of trust, and may create an ‘us and them’ sense of privilege or lack of it in the use-case scenarios of AI technology interactions in digital systems and services [13].

5 The integrity of the knowledge commons

Katz and Gandel [61] foresaw the coming challenges of maintainability for the “record keeping and human memory sharing” of digitally stored knowledge and information. Document authorship, equal access to information, privately financed information discovery, and archival appraisal based largely on popularity [61] are all more problematic today than ever. While we have previously noted numerous positives and negatives of what AI brings to interacting with the KC, there are increasing threats from the direct and indirect impact of AI on the quality and diverse range of KC content itself, and subsequent trust in it.

Surfacing a diverse range of opinions or sources may be problematic. Burton et al. [10] state “when an LLM is used in a collective process to aggregate information, it is

most likely to generate responses that reflect the opinions or beliefs that appear most frequently in the training data”. Therefore certain viewpoints may be underrepresented or excluded entirely from the training data, leading LLMs to provide responses that neglect alternative opinions or less prevalent facts. As people interact with the model and treat it as an authority, the wider horizons of diversity shrink, though this is not a problem only caused by AI and LLMs [62].

The influx of often GenAI low quality content is an increasing problem to search and discovery of online information. Bayer et al. [63] list misinformation, disinformation and propaganda as the key types of fake or low quality content, and this now includes deepfakes¹⁴, a more problematic type of fake content [64]. The exponential increase in ‘synthetic content’ - misinformation, lack of accuracy and deepfakes, all contribute to resultant erosion of trust in mainstream news media or general access to expert content of other types [12, 65]. Though low quality content in the KC is not a unique issue of GenAI¹⁵, it may be the sheer volume of synthetic low quality content that is a bigger problem, as GenAI makes it much easier for more mis/disinformation to be generated and shared at scale [66]. GenAI ‘AI slop’¹⁶ and ‘pink slime journalism’¹⁷ continue to proliferate on the Internet, often with no other purpose than to ‘game’ the SEO system to generate clicks and revenue [67]. An associated problem is the increasing danger of ‘recursion’, that slop and pink slime content finds its way back into LLM training data and begins to deteriorate the accuracy and quality of LLM output.

The quality of content and level of trust in journalism contributes to ‘epistemic agency’ of citizens and supports democratic values [68, 69], however, erosion of trust in news content due to partisan, factually incorrect or misleading pink slime is an increasing problem (e.g. [67, 69, 70]). Coeckelbergh signals the importance of what people know and how they come to know it in relation to ‘the knowledge basis of democracy’, and D’Arma et al. voice similar concerns about citizen epistemic rights for knowledge and awareness in will formation [23]. Of particular interest to this paper, Coeckelbergh notes the influence of the social on belief formation being related to a wider knowledge community and something like “collective knowledge”. Perhaps this can be taken here in the context of prevalent knowledge cultures of the Internet, and citizen digital literacy awareness to navigate and interact with the KC (e.g. [64]). It can be argued that knowledge seeking in ad-hoc urbanised learning can

¹⁴ A definition of deepfake: “videos and other media generated by machine learning algorithms in which a person in an existing image or video is (partly) replaced with someone else’s likeness” Coeckelbergh, 2023

¹⁵ Spam policies for Google web search list Cloaking, Doorway Abuse, Hacking Content, Keyword Stuffing, Link Spam and many other techniques to ‘game’ search ranking results with misleading or malign web content. <https://developers.google.com/search/docs/essentials/spam-policies>

¹⁶ AI Slop https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/AI_slop

¹⁷ Pink Slime Journalism https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Pink-slime_journalism

be an aspect of “a deliberative and participative democracy, (where) citizens are supposed to have knowledge about the issues at hand” [68]. These issues may well be localised, for example contested urban planning and development, or around civic support for better urban liveability. In this way the quality, trust and custodianship of the localised KC is important for citizen democratic self-realisation.

5.1 The potential for AI to act as guardian of knowledge

The conundrum of both encouraging GenAI content, and yet at the same time needing methods by which it can be detected and if necessary prohibited, for example in formal education assessed work, remains an on-going challenge. While AI content detectors proliferate¹⁸, they seem to offer varying results that are unreliable [71], and detecting GenAI content to measure truthfulness, accuracy and original sources is another serious challenge. Aljebreen et al. [70] investigate how to trace pink slime journalism in tweets, and Bhattacharjee & Liu [72] focus on using ChatGPT to differentiate between human and AI written texts. Knott et al. [73] suggest that in order to regulate public access to GenAI tools, “any organization developing a foundation model intended for public use must demonstrate a reliable detection mechanism for the content it generates, as a condition of its public release”. But Sadasivan et al. [74] show that “practical applications of AI-text detectors can become unreliable and invalid”, and “the cost of misidentification by a detector can be huge”. Burton et al. [10] propose ‘truly open LLMs’, and ‘better access to computational resources and LLMs for Researchers’, alongside ‘greater oversight of how LLMs are used and what harms they cause in the real world’. They suggest imposing and enforcing restrictions for what LLM models can and cannot be used for, and methods where LLM users themselves could be leveraged for participatory, post-deployment oversight, similar to Wikipedia moderation¹⁹, or participatory AI techniques in Berditchevskaia et al. [75]. It remains to be seen how LLM regulation may develop in coming years.

The cost and value of the knowledge commons

One might argue that it is in the interest of the biggest of the private companies - who may stand to make the most profit - to act as custodians and invest in methods to protect and maintain the KC. As Burton et al. [10] point out, the risk of increased disincentive to contribute to the KC may be a serious threat to its maintenance and growth. New content is essential to develop more accurate and advanced AI tools and technologies, so mechanisms must exist to encourage it. Currently, it appears that LLMs may run out of new data to train on [76] or be prevented from using more of the KC to train on [77].

¹⁸ For example, Zapier’s “The best AI content detectors in 2024” <https://zapier.com/blog/ai-content-detector/>

¹⁹ Wikipedia Moderation <https://design.wikimedia.org/blog/2020/07/30/content-moderation-anti-vandalism-wikipedia.html>

Though the financial value of user interactions data has steadily grown in recent years [78, 79], content and data value is not only measured in economic terms, but may provide other aspects of return for a user. Brynjolfsson et al. [80] researched the value of using data goods to individual wellbeing, where for example, compensation might be paid to forego using a digital app or service. They noted “a typical U.S. user of Facebook might require \$48 per month to forgo that data”. This raises interesting issues regarding the use-to-value for users themselves, considered in the context of Burton et al.’s comments regarding disincentivisation to contribute new content, and begins to reflect the imaginaries of Krikorian [81], who tells a story of an age of ‘free exploitation’ of knowledge. Free to access and free of charge to those who “produce their quota of creativity units” [81], this rather prescient but ominous vision of a fully commercialised human-in-the-loop creativity production scenario in ‘the age of intellectual property’ seems eerily close to our current reality.

Other major issues that potentially impact the KC are financial cost of developing and deploying AI technologies that may impact future AI application availability and access (e.g. [10, 82, 83]), and the demand for energy to process generative or analytical AI data, set to increase exponentially [84–86], though new solutions may be on the horizon (e.g. [87]). Energy requirements may additionally cause substantial cost to the environment, with major companies now seeking new solutions such as Small Modular Reactors²⁰.

6 Concluding remarks

This paper has attempted to consider the digital knowledge content and knowledge seeking interactions of humans and non-humans in the knowledge commons (KC), in light of developing capabilities of AI. The KC is loosely regarded as all the open, free-access knowledge content available to anyone via the Internet, both amateur and expert knowledge, and sometimes also referred to as ‘collective intelligence’. This paper has argued that access and contribution to the KC is part of the process of knowing and will forming that sit at the foundation of democratic life, manifesting as skills of collaboration, debate and digital literacy for understanding and exchanging ideas in virtual and real worlds. The ‘participatory media embraced by the general public’ form “the social foundations that have always supported science, academic research and creativity” Bollier [24]. However, the erosion of trust in online information is increasing, exacerbated by GenAI technologies, which in turn may disincentivise the public from contributing new knowledge, in some measure due to LLM obfuscation of individual contributions.

²⁰ Tech companies want small nuclear reactors. Here’s how they’d work. <https://www.sciencenews.org/article/small-modular-nuclear-reactors-amazon>

The tacit arrangements of ‘give and take’ in the KC that have emerged over the past two decades might not be sufficient to preserve the KC into the future, with or without AI assistance, so perhaps it is time to rethink how we define the role of our ‘collective intelligence’ KC in society. In 1999 Stiglitz proposed that knowledge (digital commons or otherwise) should be formalised as a global public good, where a “central public policy implication of public goods is that the state must play some role” [25]. The digital KC resource as we have discussed could be formalised as a global public good, through firmer legislative custodianship and maintenance, with national and international governance for shared responsibilities by educational and civic bodies, non-profit information preservation groups and technological platforms. This might entail legal obligations, for example requiring fake and low quality content detection and regulatory custodianship of training sources to be done by AI technology companies themselves (e.g. EU AI Act²¹, and [53]). As Stiglitz reminds us, access and dissemination of knowledge is as important as creation of knowledge, and ‘the Internet is a tool of immense power in sharing knowledge’. For both AI technologies and knowledge economies to flourish, the KC as a global public good is better positioned to provide reliable and trustworthy knowledge, particularly for urban smart learning as part of citizen participatory democracy.

References

1. Lister, P.: The pedagogy of experience complexity for smart learning: considerations for designing urban digital citizen learning activities. *Smart Learning Environments*. 8, 8 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40561-021-00154-x>.
2. Lister, P.: A smarter knowledge commons for smart learning. *Smart Learning Environments*. 5, 8, (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40561-018-0056-z>.
3. Lister, P.: Future-Present Learning in Place: postdigital learning at the scale of the city. In: Streitz, N.A. and Konomi, S. (eds.) *Distributed, Ambient and Pervasive Interactions. HCHI 2024. Lecture Notes in Computer Science*. Springer, Cham (2024).
4. Lister, P.: Creating a city for all of us: a role for the Fediverse in archiving civic urban memory. *Digital Society*. (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s44206-024-00137-8>.
5. Jarrahi, M.H., Askay, D., Eshraghi, A., Smith, P.: Artificial intelligence and knowledge management: A partnership between human and AI. *Business Horizons*. 66, 87–99 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bushor.2022.03.002>.
6. Paul, A., Chauhan, S., Dutta, D.: Mobile-based image interpretation and geotagging using artificial intelligence and open-source geospatial technology. *Applied Geomatics*. 15, 795–805 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12518-023-00522-x>.
7. Nizzoli, L., Avvenuti, M., Tesconi, M., Cresci, S.: Geo-semantic-parsing: AI-powered geoparsing by traversing semantic knowledge graphs. *Decision Support Systems*. 136, 113346 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dss.2020.113346>.

²¹ The EU AI Act <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/regulatory-framework-ai>

8. Akhilesh, K.B.: Smart Technologies - Scope and Applications. In: Akhilesh, K., B., and Möller, D.P.F. (eds.) *Smart Technologies Scope and Applications*. Springer (2020). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-13-7139-4_1.
9. Pérez-Ortiz, M., Dormann, C., Rogers, Y., Bulathwela, S., Kreitmayer, S., Yilmaz, E., Noss, R., Shawe-Taylor, J.: X5Learn: A Personalised Learning Companion at the Intersection of AI and HCI. In: *Companion Proceedings of the 26th International Conference on Intelligent User Interfaces (IUI '21 Companion*. pp. 70–74. Association for Computing Machinery (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3397482.3450721>.
10. Burton, J.W., Lopez-Lopez, E., Hechtlinger, S.: How large language models can reshape collective intelligence. *Nature Human Behavior*. 8, 1643–1655 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41562-024-01959-9>.
11. Verma, P.: The rise of AI fake news is creating a ‘misinformation superspreader.’ *The Washington Post* (2023).
12. Claburn, T.: Wiley shuts 19 scholarly journals amid AI paper mill problems: Fake science challenges academic publishing. *The Register* (2024).
13. Lévisque, M.: Analog Privilege. *New York University Journal of Legislation and Public Policy*. 26, 625–696 (2024).
14. Hwang, G.: Definition, framework and research issues of smart learning environments - a context-aware ubiquitous learning perspective. *Smart Learning Environments*. 1, 4 (2014). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40561-014-0004-5>.
15. Borkowska, K., Osborne, M.: Locating the fourth helix: Rethinking the role of civil society in developing smart learning cities. *International Review of Education*. 64, 355–372 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11159-018-9723-0>.
16. Hess, C.: Mapping the New Commons. In: *Twelfth Biennial Conference of the International Association for the Study of the Commons*. pp. 14–18. Syracuse University SURFACE, Cheltenham, UK (2008).
17. Lane, A.: Who puts the Education into Open Educational Content? In: Katz, R.N. (ed.) *The Tower and The Cloud*. Educause (2008).
18. Chayka, K.: *How the Internet Turned Us Into Content Machines*. New Yorker (2022).
19. Bruun, M.H.: Communities and the commons: Open access and community ownership of the Urban Commons. In: *Urban Commons: Rethinking the City*. Routledge (2015).
20. Gudeman, S.F.: *The Anthropology of Economy: Community, Market, and Culture*, (2001).
21. Berlingeur, M.: *New Commons: Towards a Necessary Reappraisal*. Popular Communication (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1080/15405702.2020.1781857>.
22. Lohmann, R.: The Commons: a Multidisciplinary Approach to Nonprofit Organisation, Voluntary Action and Philanthropy. *Nonprofit and Voluntary Sector Quarterly*. 21, 309–324 (1992). <https://doi.org/10.1177/089976409202100308>.
23. D’Arma, A., Aslama Horowitz, M., Lehtisaari, K., Nieminen, H.: Introduction: The Epistemic Turn. In: Aslama Horowitz, M., Nieminen, H., Lehtisaari, K., and D’Arma, A. (eds.) *Epistemic Rights in the Era of Digital Disruption*. Palgrave Macmillan, Cham (2024). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-45976-4_1.

24. Bollier, D.: The Growth of the Commons Paradigm. In: Hess, C. and Ostrom, E. (eds.) *Understanding Knowledge as a Commons: From Theory to Practice*. MIT Press (2007).
25. Stiglitz, J.E.: Knowledge as a global public good. In: Kaul, I., Grunberg, I., and Stern, M.A. (eds.) *Global public goods: International cooperation in the 21st century*. pp. 308–325. Oxford university Press (1999).
26. Fröding, B., Peterson, M.: Friendly AI. *Ethics Information Technology*. 23, 207–214 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10676-020-09556-w>.
27. Sun, Q., Li, Y., Alturki, E., Murthy, S.M.K., Schuller, B.W.: Towards Friendly AI: A Comprehensive Review and New Perspectives on Human-AI Alignment, <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2412.15114>, (2024). <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2412.15114>.
28. Dede, C.: Planning for Neomillennial Learning Styles. *EDUCAUSE Quarterly*. 28, 7–12 (2005).
29. Dunleavy, M., Dede, C.: Augmented Reality Teaching and Learning. In: Spector, J., Merrill, M., Elen, J., and Bishop, M. (eds.) *Handbook of Research on Educational Communications and Technology*. pp. 735–745. Springer (2014). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-3185-5_59.
30. McKenna, H.P.: Rethinking Learning in the Smart City: Innovating Through Involvement, Inclusivity, and Interactivities with Emerging Technologies. In: Gil-Garcia, J., Pardo, T., and Nam, T. (eds.) *Smarter as the New Urban Agenda. Public Administration and Information Technology*, Cham (2016). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-17620-8_5.
31. Buchem, I., Pérez-Sanagustín, M.: Personal Learning Environments in Smart Cities: Current Approaches and Future Scenarios. *Open Education Europa eLearning Papers*. 35, 1–14 (2013).
32. Gros, B.: The design of smart educational environments. *Smart Learning Environments*. 3,15, (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40561-016-0039-x>.
33. Giovanella, C., Martens, A., Zualkernan, I.: Grand Challenge Problem 1: People Centered Smart ‘Cities’ Through Smart City Learning. In: Eberle, J. (ed.) *Grand Challenge Problems in Technology-Enhanced Learning II: MOOCs and Beyond*. SpringerBriefs in Education (2016). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-12562-6_2.
34. Liu, D., Huang, R., Wosinski, M.: *Characteristics and Framework of Smart Learning*. Springer (2017). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-10-4343-7_3.
35. Dron, J., Anderson, T.: On the Nature and Value of Social Software for Learning. In: *Teaching Crowds: Learning and Social Media*. pp. 3–34 (2014). <https://doi.org/10.15215/aupress/9781927356807.01>.
36. Lister, P.: What are we Supposed to be Learning? Motivation and Autonomy in Smart Learning Environments. In: Streitz, N. and Konomi, S. (eds.) *Distributed, Ambient and Pervasive Interactions. Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, Springer Cham (2021). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-77015-0_17.
37. Asemi, A., Asemi, A.: Artificial Intelligence(AI) application in Library Systems in Iran: A taxonomy study. *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)* (2018).

38. Ahmed, M., Mukhopadhyay, M., Mukhopadhyay, P.: Automated Knowledge Organisation: AI/ML-based Subject Indexing System for Libraries. *DESIDOC Journal of Library & Information Technology*. 43, 45–54 (2023).
39. Hu, H.: Research on the Application of Big Data and Artificial Intelligence in Search Engine. *International Journal of Computer Science and Information Technology*. 2, 124–130 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.62051/ijcsit.v2n1.14>.
40. Zhu, R.: *Geospatial Knowledge Graphs*. International Encyclopedia of Geography: People, the Earth, Environment and Technology. Wiley (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118786352.wbieg2207>.
41. Sheth, A., Padhee, S., Gyrard, A.: Knowledge Graphs and Knowledge Networks: The Story in Brief. *IEEE Internet Computing*. 23, 67–75 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1109/MIC.2019.2928449>.
42. Janowicz, K., Gao, S., McKenzie, G., Hu, Y., Bhaduri, B.: GeoAI: spatially explicit artificial intelligence techniques for geographic knowledge discovery and beyond. *International Journal of Geographical Information Science*. 34, 625–636 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1080/13658816.2019.1684500>.
43. Dreibelbis Forlini, E.: What Is ChatGPT Vision? 7 Ways People Are Using This Wild New Feature. *PC Mag* (2023).
44. Ge, Y., Liu, S., Fu, Z., Tan, J., Li, Z., Xu, S., Li, Y., Xian, Y., Zhang, Y.: A Survey on Trustworthy Recommender Systems. *ACM Transactions on Recommender Systems*. 3, (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3652891>.
45. Duricic, T., Kowald, D., Lacic, E., Lex, E.: Beyond-accuracy: a review on diversity, serendipity, and fairness in recommender systems based on graph neural networks. *Frontiers in Big Data*. 6, (2023). <https://doi.org/10.3389/fdata.2023.1251072>.
46. Ziarani, R.J., Ravanmehr, R.: Serendipity in recommender systems: A systematic literature review. *Journal Of Computer Science And Technology*. 36, 375–396 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11390-020-0135-9>.
47. del Valle, J.I., Lara, F.: AI-powered recommender systems and the preservation of personal autonomy. *AI & Society*. 39, 2479–2491 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00146-023-01720-2>.
48. Zhao, Z.: Recommender Systems in the Era of Large Language Models (LLMs). *IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering*. 36, 6889–6907 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1109/TKDE.2024.3392335>.
49. Wu, L., Zheng, Z., Qiu, Z.: A survey on large language models for recommendation. *World Wide Web*. 27, (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11280-024-01291-2>.
50. Rao, J., Gao, S., Li, M., Huang, Q.: A privacy-preserving framework for location recommendation using decentralized collaborative machine learning. *Transactions in GIS*. 25, 1153–1175 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1111/tgis.12769>.
51. Vannieuwenhuyze, J., Smets, A., Gebert, M., Ballon, P.: Methodological analysis of personalization in urban recommender systems by distance measures. *Telematics and Informatics*. 71, 101818 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tele.2022.101818>.

52. Brank, J., Leban, G., Grobelnik, M.: Annotating Documents with Relevant Wikipedia Concepts. In: Proceedings of the Slovenian KDD Conference on Data Mining and Data Warehouses (SiKDD. , Ljubljana, Slovenia (2017).
53. Huang, S., Siddarth, D.: Generative AI and the Digital Commons, <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2303.11074>, (2023).
<https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2303.11074>.
54. Rubin, J.H., Rubin, I.S.: Qualitative Interviewing, The Art of hearing Data. Sage Publications (2012).
55. Thompson, B., Dhaliwal, M.P., Frisch, P., Domhan, T., Federico, M.: A Shocking Amount of the Web is Machine Translated: Insights from Multi-Way Parallelism. ArXiv:2401.05749v2. (2024). <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2401.05749>.
56. Alhanai, T., Kasumovic, A., Ghassemi, M., Zitzelberger, A., Lundin, J., Chabot-Couture, G.: Bridging the Gap: Enhancing LLM Performance for Low-Resource African Languages with New Benchmarks, Fine-Tuning, and Cultural Adjustments, <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2412.12417>, (2024).
<https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2412.12417>.
57. Robinson, N.R., Ogayo, P., Mortensen, D.R., Neubig, G.: ChatGPT MT: Competitive for high-(but not low-) resource languages, <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2309.07423>, (2023).
<https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2309.07423>.
58. Rawat, A.S., Sadhanala, V., Rostamizadeh, A., Chakrabarti, A., Jitkrittum, W., Feinberg, V., Kumar, S.: A Little Help Goes a Long Way: Efficient LLM Training by Leveraging Small LMs, <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2410.18779>, (2024).
<https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2410.18779>.
59. Esposito, E.: Artificial communication: How algorithms produce social intelligence. MIT Press (2022).
60. Casebourne, I., Shi, S., Hogan, M.: Using AI to Support Education for Collective Intelligence. International Journal of Artificial Intelligence in Education. (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40593-024-00437-7>.
61. Katz, R.N., Gandel, P.B.: The Tower, the Cloud, and Posterity. In: Katz, R.N. (ed.) The Tower and The Cloud. Educause (2008).
62. Chayka, K.: Filterworld: how algorithms flattened culture. DoubleDay. Penguin Random House (2024).
63. Bayer, J., Bitiukova, N., Bard, P., Szakács, J., Alemanno, A., Uszkiewicz, E.: Disinformation and Propaganda – Impact on the Functioning of the Rule of Law in the EU and its Member States. In: European Parliament, LIBE Committee, Policy Department for Citizens’ Rights and Constitutional Affairs (2019).
64. Twomey, J., Ching, D., Aylett, M.P., Quayle, M., Linehan, C., Murphy, G.: Do deepfake videos undermine our epistemic trust? A thematic analysis of tweets that discuss deepfakes in the Russian invasion of Ukraine. Plos One. 18, 0291668 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0291668>.
65. Wahl-Jorgensen, K., Carlson, M.: Conjecturing fearful futures: Journalistic discourses on deepfakes. Journalism Practice. 15, 803–820 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1080/17512786.2021.1908838>.

66. Yum, I.: Language Agents and Malevolent Design. *Philosophy & Technology*. 37, 104 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13347-024-00794-0>.
67. Adami, M.: AI-generated slop is quietly conquering the internet. Is it a threat to journalism or a problem that will fix itself? Reuters Institute, University of Oxford (2024).
68. Coeckelbergh, M.: Democracy, epistemic agency, and AI: political epistemology in times of artificial intelligence. *AI Ethics*. 3, 1341–1350 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43681-022-00239-4>.
69. Goudarzi, S.: To protect democratic values, journalism must save itself. *Bulletin of the Atomic Scientists*. 80, 314–320 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1080/00963402.2024.2388468>.
70. Aljebreen, A., Meng, W., Dragut, E.C.: Analysis and Detection of “Pink Slime” Websites in Social Media Posts. In: *Proceedings of WWW '24, the ACM Web Conference 2024*. pp. 2572–2581 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3589334>.
71. Weber-Wulff, D., Anohina-Naumeca, A., Bjelobaba, S.: Testing of detection tools for AI-generated text. *Int J Educ Integr*. 19, 26 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40979-023-00146-z>.
72. Bhattacharjee, A., Liu, H.: Fighting Fire with Fire: Can ChatGPT Detect AI-generated Text? *Arxiv* (2023). <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2308.01284>.
73. Knott, A., Pedreschi, D., Chatila, R.: Generative AI models should include detection mechanisms as a condition for public release. *Ethics Inf Technol*. 25, 55 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10676-023-09728-4>.
74. Sadasivan, V.S., Kumar, A., Balasubramanian, S., Wang, W., Feizi, S.: Can AI-generated text be reliably detected?, <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2303.11156>, (2023). <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2303.11156>.
75. Berditchevskaia, A., Malliaraki, E., Peach, K.: *Participatory AI for Humanitarian Innovation: A Briefing Paper*. Nesta (2021).
76. Villalobos, P., Sevilla, J., Heim, L., Besiroglu, T., Hobbhahn, M., Ho, A.: Will we run out of data? An analysis of the limits of scaling datasets in Machine Learning, <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2211.04325>, (2022). <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2211.04325>.
77. Longpre, S.: Consent in Crisis: The Rapid Decline of the AI Data Commons. In: *NEURIPS 2024 – 38th Annual Conference on Neural Information Processing Systems* (2024).
78. Thirani, V., Gupta, A.: The value of data. *World Economic Forum* (2017).
79. Rea, N., Sutton, A.: Putting a value on data, <https://www.pwc.co.uk/data-analytics/documents/putting-value-on-data.pdf>, (2019).
80. Brynjolfsson, E., Collis, A., Eggers, F.: Using massive online choice experiments to measure changes in well-being. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*. 116, 7250–7255 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1815663116>.
81. Krikorian, G.: Social Mutations in the Future. In: Krikorian, G. and Kapczynski, A. (eds.) *Access to Knowledge in The Age of Intellectual Property*. Zone Books. MIT Press (2010).
82. Likhadzed, V., Klubnikin, A.: How much does AI cost in 2024? Well, it depends. *ITRex Group* (2024).

83. Goldman, S.: The hidden reason AI costs are soaring—and it's not because Nvidia chips are more expensive. *Fortune, Yahoo Finance* (2024).
84. Silva, P.M.: *Epistemology of Incidental Learning*. Faculty of the Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University. Doctoral Dissertation (2007).
85. Luccioni, S., Jernite, Y., Strubell, E.: Power Hungry Processing: Watts Driving the Cost of AI Deployment? In: *Proceedings of the 2024 ACM Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency (FAccT '24)*. pp. 85–99. Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3630106.3658542>.
86. Chauhan, H.: Artificial Intelligence (AI) Energy Consumption Is Jumping At a Scary Pace: 2 Stocks That Could Surge Thanks to This Trend. *The Motley Fool. Nasdaq* (2024).
87. Blancquart, A.: The inevitable limits of exponential growth in Artificial Intelligence and EvoChip's solution to compute AI models in a chip a magnitude faster. *White Paper. Evochip* (2024).